

Technical note

The data repository for the IMPASTO project

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Abstract:

As a part of the IMPASTO project, the data repository for the IMPASTO project results was set up on the address <http://haos.ff.bg.ac.rs/IMPASTO>. The Faculty of Physics, University of Belgrade is the host of the repository. The repository currently contains the data from four numerical experiments that were done during the IMPASTO project, together with supporting software for data download and data processing. Access to the repository and data is free without any specific restrictions.

Data can be browsed and downloaded file by file, or using prepared bash scripts with *wget* free software package, that enables download of the whole experiment dataset without repository browsing.

For data processing a simple Fortran program is available for download, together with a short user guide for compilation and execution. The program enables users to read the raw model results and to convert data into the format that can be analyzed using The Grid Analysis and Display System (GrADS).